

Dietary replacement of soybean with different levels of *Hermetia illucens* meal during grower and finisher phases in broilers: effects on live performances and meat quality

Soglia Francesca, Zampiga Marco, Petracci Massimiliano, Sirri Federico

Department of Agricultural and Food Sciences, Alma Mater Studiorum - University of Bologna, Italy

Session: Processing and Products
October 4th 2022

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Introduction

Increasing population and income have driven-up demand for animal-based proteins leading to an **increased need for animal feed**

- Relatively simple to reproduce and rear
- Non-pest species (no environmental risk)
- High protein and essential AA content (e.g., lysine, valine and arginine)

- Production on regulated feedstuffs
- Performance parameters?

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Aim of the study

Assess the impact of the **replacement of the commercial soybean-based diet** with an *Hermetia illucens* meal (IM) during both the grower and finisher diets on both the **growth and production performances** of broiler chickens as well as on the **main quality traits of breast meat**.

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Material and Methods

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N = 1,000 1-day-old
Ross 308
male chicks

Treatments

Conventional corn-wheat-soybean diet (**CON**)

CON + 9% protein replacement with *Hermetia illucens* meal (**9IM**)

CON + 18% protein replacement with *Hermetia illucens* meal (**18IM**)

(7 replicates/group)

Hermetia illucens meal obtained from larvae reared on organic substrates

Growth and productive performances

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Analyses

- **Quality traits** – pH, color
- **Technological properties** – Water Holding Capacity (drip loss, cooking loss) & Tenderness (Warner Bratzler shear force)
- **Oxidation** – proteins (carbonyls) & lipid (ThioBarbituric Acid Reactive Substances)

Statistical analyses

Data were analyzed through **One-way ANOVA** by considering the level of the dietary replacement of soybean meal with IM (i.e., 0, 9, 18%) as main effect. When significant, means were subsequently separated by Tukey-HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Results

Effect on growth and production performances

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	CON	9IM	18IM	SEM	p-value
Body weight (g/bird)	3,205 a	3,001 b	2,441 c	114.6	***
Daily weight gain (g/bird/d)	70.6 a	66.4 b	53.2 c	2.65	***
Daily feed intake (g/bird/d)*	113.6 a	113.8 a	102.8 b	4.00	***
Feed intake (kg/bird)*	5.135 a	5.133 a	4.645 b	0.17	***
Feed conversion rate*	1.610 b	1.716 b	1.939 a	0.08	***
Mortality (%)	2.38	1.39	4.76	0.13	ns

***=p<0.001; ns=not significant.

a-c = mean values followed by different letters significantly differ among the groups (p<0.05).

* = data corrected for mortality.

Results

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Quality traits

	CON	9IM	18IM	SEM	p-value
Fillet weight (g)	274.9	267.5	250.2	5.77	ns
Ultimate pH (pHu)	5.79 a	5.64 b	5.64 b	0.02	*
Lightness - L*	57.24 b	59.78 a	56.46 b	0.61	**
Redness - a*	1.59	1.28	1.93	0.11	ns
Yellowness - b*	6.78	7.08	6.79	0.19	ns

*=p<0.05; **=p<0.01; ns=not significant;

a,b = mean values followed by different letters significantly differ among the groups (p<0.05).

Results

Technological properties

	CON	9IM	18IM	SEM	p-value
Drip loss (%)	2.14	2.38	1.77	0.17	ns
Cooking loss (%)	19.1	20.2	20.1	0.4	ns
Shear Force (kg)	1.56	1.95	1.88	0.07	ns

ns = not significant

Oxidation

	CON	9IM	18IM	SEM	p-value
Carbonyls (nmol/mg of protein)	0.24	0.79	0.42	0.11	ns
TBARS (mg MDA/kg of meat)	2.27	1.98	2.01	0.10	ns

ns = not significant

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Conclusions

- From the perspective of meat quality the dietary replacement of the commercial corn-wheat-soybean diet with an *Hermetia illucens* meal may represent a possible strategy to improve the sustainability of the feed without negative implication on meat quality traits.
- High level of inclusion is severely limited by the impairment of the production performances.

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Acknowledgments and Funding

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This research was undertaken under the NextGenProteins (Transformation of Biomass into Next Generation Proteins for Food and Feed) project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, Call H2020-LC-SFS-17-2019, grant agreement no. 862704 (<https://nextgenproteins.eu/>).

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Chemical composition of the *Hermetia illucens* larvae meal

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Composition (as is)	%
Dry Matter	95-98
Crude protein	>55
Total fat	≤11
Ash	≤11
Chitin	≤6

Fatty Acids profile	%FA
Saturated FA	68.6
Lauric acid	40.1
Palmitic acid	15.1
Myristic acid	8.5
Monounsaturated FA	17.0
Oleic acid	13.5
Polyunsaturated FA	14.4
Linoleic acid	12.8

Amino Acids profile	%AA
Alanine	7.53
Arginine	5.41
Aspartic acid	9.95
Cystine	0.90
Glutamic acid	13.14
Glycine	5.76
Histidine	3.43
Isoleucine	4.82
Leucine	7.46
Lysine	6.13
Methionine	1.81
Phenylalanine	4.51
Proline	6.05
Serine	4.53
Threonine	4.37
Tryptophan	1.50
Tyrosine	6.27
Valine	6.70

